

PARENTS ARE RESPONSIBLE FOR THEIR CHILDREN RECEIVE EDUCATION POSSIBLE.

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Abstract. Homeschooling is increasing in popularity. Parents choose homeschooling for four reasons: dissatisfaction with the public schools, concern about academic excellence, the wish to build stronger family bonds, and the desire to freely impart religious values. Research has shown that homeschooled children do well on standardized tests and are welcome at even highly competitive colleges. Yet traditional educators have serious concerns, among them fear that the academic quality of homeschooling may be substandard and that homeschooled children lose the benefits of interacting with their peers.

Keywords: Homeschooling, traditional schools, “hothouse relationship”, educate, pedagogical methods.

РОДИТЕЛИ НЕСУТ ОТВЕТСТВЕННОСТЬ ЗА ТО, ЧТОБЫ ИХ ДЕТИ ПОЛУЧАЛИ ВОЗМОЖНОЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ.

Аннотация. Популярность домашнего обучения растет. Родители выбирают домашнее обучение по четырем причинам: неудовлетворенность государственными школами, беспокойство по поводу успеваемости, желание укрепить семейные узы и желание свободно распространять религиозные ценности. Исследования показали, что дети, обучающиеся на дому, хорошо сдают стандартизированные тесты и их приветствуют даже в высококонкурентных колледжах. Тем не менее, у традиционных педагогов есть серьезные опасения, в том числе опасения, что академическое качество домашнего обучения может быть некачественным и что дети, обучающиеся на дому, потеряют преимущества взаимодействия со своими сверстниками.

Ключевые слова: домашнее обучение, традиционная школа, «комнатные отношения», воспитание, педагогические методы.

This article should focus on how best to educate our children, not on parental rights. With their resources, experience, and expertise, traditional schools can do this best. High-minded arguments about parental rights are all well and good, but a child’s future is at stake.

You cannot make up for bad schooling, and no one has developed a reliable method for ensuring the quality of home schooling. This debate is therefore not about a right and not about a choice parents have no right to choose to fail their child in her or his education.

Hundreds of educational researchers and experts with many years of experience labor to ensure that schools employ the best pedagogical methods. How presumptuous of parents to think that they know better. Public schools may not be perfect, but they will only get worse as those who can afford to opt to educate at home.

It’s a pretty good bet that parents won’t be as good as a teacher, unless they are a member of that profession. Furthermore, even if parents excel in one area, will they cover all the things a

school does? Support groups can't make a parent into a teacher, any more than a book on engineering makes one an engineer.

Schools beat homes on the two fronts the affirmative has mentioned. For example, homes are very unlikely to have extensive science laboratories. Also, having a parent ask a young child to switch from "learning mode" to "play mode" in the same environment must be very confusing.

For the older child, homeschooling gives ample opportunities for abuse for pushing activities they enjoy instead of a lesson or manipulating the parent to slack off "just this once." Schools are for learning that's their essence, their function. The home is an altogether more complex environment, ill-suited to instruction.

The benefits of education in a wider context more than offset this objection. Of course, the state doesn't just leave high achievers and strugglers to rot! While students may not get individual attention, the experience of growing up alongside less and more able students and those with special needs produces individuals with a greater understanding of their society. Furthermore, students with special needs are those that most need the state's enormous resources.

Parents and children spending day after day at home are sometimes subject to a phenomenon sociologists call the "hothouse relationship." The closeness between them becomes exclusive, with reaction to outsiders almost aggressive by instinct. Such a relationship makes adaptation to life in a wider community even more difficult when the time comes.

Those who wish their children to be educated in a religious environment have the chance to send them to a religious school, the quality of which can be monitored by the state. Furthermore, what is the guarantee that the moral structure parents might be instilling in their children is beneficial? Exclusivity of belief is extremely unhealthy.

Children should engage society as a whole so that they can understand other people's beliefs and points of view. In addition, public schools must teach the dispassionate conclusions of science, regardless of parents' religious beliefs.

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